

Immunocompetent PDMS-Free Organ-on-Chip Model of Cervical Cancer Integrating Patient-Specific Cervical Fibroblasts and Neutrophils

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Despite preventive measures and available treatments, cervical cancer still ranks as the fourth most prevalent cancer among women worldwide and remains the leading cause of cancer death in women in many developing countries. To gain further insights into pathogenesis and to develop novel (immuno)therapies, more sophisticated human models recreating patient heterogeneities and including aspects of the tumor microenvironment are urgently required. A novel polydimethylsiloxane-free microfluidic platform, designed specifically for the generation and cultivation of cervical cancerous tissue, is introduced. The microscale open-top tissue chambers of the cervical cancer-on-chip (CCoC) enable facile generation and long-term cultivation of SiHa spheroids in co-culture with donor-derived cervical fibroblasts. The resulting 3D tissue emulates physiological architecture and allows dissection of distinct effects of the stromal tissue on cancer viability and growth. Treatment with cisplatin at clinically-relevant routes of administration and dosing highlights the platform's applicability for drug testing. Moreover, the model is amenable for integration and recruitment of donor-derived neutrophils from the microvasculature-like channel into the tissue, all while retaining their ability to produce neutrophil extracellular traps. In the future, the immunocompetent CCoC featuring donor-specific primary cells and tumor spheroids has the potential to contribute to the development of new (immuno)therapeutic options.

2020, representing 6.5% of all female cancers.^[1] Infection with human papillomavirus (HPV) stands as a necessary yet insufficient cause of cervical cancer development.^[2] HPV infections are the most common sexually transmitted infection in the United States, with more than 80% of sexually active individuals being infected with HPV at least once during their lifetime.^[3] More than 90% of HPV infections within the cervix resolve naturally,^[4] however, a persistent infection can lead to cervical cancer. A major breakthrough in the battle against HPV-linked diseases was the introduction of prophylactic vaccines designed to thwart high-risk HPV strains HPV16 and HPV18. The remarkably efficacious primary (vaccine) and secondary (screening) preventive measures have rendered cervical cancer nearly entirely preventable. Unfortunately, insufficient vaccine availability and vaccination coverage persist as challenges, resulting in cervical cancer still being the leading cause of cancer death in 36 countries, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Since HPV-associated cancers remain a pressing global health concern,^[1] the Director

General of the World Health Organization (WHO) announced a global call for action to eliminate cervical cancer.^[5]

Despite technological advancements, many patients are still diagnosed only in an advanced stage with poor prognosis,

1. Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most frequent cancer in women worldwide with about 600 000 new cases being diagnosed in

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particularly in developing countries. For these patients, it is important to receive a timely and effective treatment, such as surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy depending on the disease stage. For early-stage disease (FIGO stage IA1-IA1) the National Comprehensive Cancer Network recommends either surgery or radiotherapy, whereas the treatment recommended for advanced stages (FIGO IIB-IVA) may be combined therapy including external beam radiation, cisplatin-containing chemotherapy, and brachytherapy. In case of metastasis and most recently in case of locally advanced malignancies, targeted therapy with bevacizumab and immunotherapy with immune checkpoint inhibitors have been applied.^[6] Frequent recurrence after treatment and the accompanying side effects and complications emphasize the necessity for alternative cervical cancer treatments that offer minimized adverse outcomes.^[7–10] Even though patients are treated based on defined guidelines, every individual patient shows a different response because of the heterogeneity of patients and their tumors. While certain prognostic factors (e.g., clinical stage, age, tumor histology, depth of invasion, tumor grade, size of primary tumor, lymph node involvement, parametrium involvement, and lymph-vascular space invasion) have been identified, many unknown factors leading to differential treatment success remain.^[11] Therefore, there is an urgent need for patient-specific *in vitro* models to properly stratify and predict the efficacy of available chemotherapeutic, targeted, and immunologic agents as well as to enable the development of novel therapeutic options. Leveraging microfluidic organ-on-chip technology, tissue engineering, and patient-derived primary cells, this study aims to improve (personalized) treatment strategies and outcomes for cervical cancer patients in the future.

The two major histological subtypes of cervical cancer are squamous-cell carcinoma (SCC) and adenocarcinomas, accounting for over 70% and almost 20% of all cervical carcinomas, respectively.^[12] Structurally, invasive SCC is characterized by cancerous nest of neoplastic epithelium infiltrating the stroma.^[13,14] Within the tumor microenvironment (TME), extensive bi-directional communication occurs between HPV-positive epithelial cells and stromal components such as fibroblasts and immune cells.^[13,15] In healthy tissue, resident, quiescent fibroblasts are responsible for extracellular matrix (ECM) homeostasis and play major roles in communicating with other cell types.^[16] In cancer, the initial fibroblast response can be tumor-suppressive through contact- and soluble factor-mediated mechanisms termed neighbor suppression.^[17] However, fibroblasts can be activated by cancer cells and undergo substantial metabolic changes in response to growth factors and the hypoxic environment. These cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) do not only represent the predominant cell type of the TME, but contribute to the malignant, anabolic phenotype of cancer cells by influencing cancer cell survival, proliferation and invasion, leukocyte infiltration, ECM remodeling, angiogenesis and chemoresistance amongst others.^[17–22]

Neutrophils (polymorphonuclear leukocytes, PMNs) are the most abundant, short-lived immune cell in humans and are considered first responder immune cells, as they are rapidly recruited to sites of infection, where they destroy invading pathogens due to their innate recognition of damage and infection and also clear cellular debris.^[23–25] Increasing evidence emphasizes the contribution of PMNs to tumor initiation, progres-

sion, metastasis, and therapeutic success. In the TME, tumor associated neutrophils (TAN) can acquire anti- (N1) or pro-tumoral (N2) properties with heterogenous effects^[26–32] making TANs a promising target for immunotherapeutic interventions.^[28,33–35] Cervical cancer is a compelling candidate for potential immunotherapeutic interventions targeting PMNs, since patients typically exhibit neutrophilia and reduced migratory capacity of peripheral blood PMNs,^[36] and PMNs are the second most abundant immune cell type in the TME of cervical carcinomas.^[15] In cervical cancer, (intratumoral) PMN density was associated with shorter progression-free survival (PFS),^[37,38] with stromal neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) as an independent prognostic factor for cervical cancer.^[39] NETs are large, toxic, web-like structures, that are released extracellularly by PMNs by a mechanism generally leading to cell death and, hence, referred to as NETosis. These structures consist mainly of adhesive, decondensed chromatin, spiked with microbicidal proteins such as citrullinated histones (H3cit) as well as granular myeloperoxidase (MPO) and neutrophil elastase (NE).^[40–42] First described as a mechanism to immobilize and kill bacteria,^[40] NETosis has since then been observed in various diseases, including cancer.^[33,42,43] NETs may possess anticarcinogenic properties by destroying cancer cells and stimulating immune cells, but also exhibit numerous pro-tumoral effects such as promotion of cancer cell proliferation and dissemination, creation of a physical barrier of encapsulated tumor cells preventing cancer cell killing by immune cells, aiding extravasation of circulating tumor cells, wakening dormant cancer cells, and driving cancer therapy resistance. Overall, presence of NETs is associated with poor prognosis in multiple cancers and some cancers have been shown to induce NET formation.^[25,29,44] In cervical cancer, NETs are associated with short recurrence-free survival,^[39] and in peripheral blood PMNs, NET levels were larger in cervical cancer patient plasma compared to healthy controls.^[45] These data suggest NETs as a potential prognostic marker and therapeutic target for the development of new generations of immunotherapies, also in combination with immune checkpoint inhibitors.^[25,29,33,39,46]

Developing more effective therapies faces a significant challenge due to a lack of *in vitro* cancer models that adequately capture the complexity of human tumors, particularly with respect to the TME and immune response. Animal models often fail to reproduce human biology.^[47] Distinct differences in cervical cancer biology between humans and mice are, for example, oncogenes E6 and E7. In mice, the HPV-E6-inhibited p53 signaling pathway plays a crucial role in triggering senescence, while in humans, the HPV-E7-inhibited retinoblastoma signaling pathway dominates. Furthermore, carcinomas that develop in transgenic mice often occur in epithelial sites elsewhere in the mouse.^[48] Patient-derived xenograft (PDX)-models capture heterogeneity, histology, and human genetic background, and generally exhibit the metastatic patterns associated with each disease. However, the most common transplantation sites for cervical cancer PDX-models are subcutaneous tissue and the subrenal capsule;^[4] immune cell deficiency, moreover, renders them unsuitable for immunotherapeutic intervention studies. On the other hand, novel bioengineering approaches toward complex microphysiological 3D cancer models promise to better emulate human tumors and TME.^[49] In this context, the sourcing of cells becomes a pivotal consideration—for in-

stance, HPV-immortalized cervical epithelia in Transwell models demonstrated greater invasive behavior when cultured on human fibroblasts as opposed to mouse fibroblasts, emphasizing the importance of employing species-specific fibroblasts in *in vitro* models. With respect to PMNs, so far, the majority of cancer research relied on animal models. However, mouse and human PMNs differ substantially in their biology and functions,^[50,51] highlighting the need for models integrating human PMNs.

In this study, we engineered a complex, human cervical cancer 3D model based on organ-on-chip technology—tumor spheroids co-cultured alongside tissue-specific cervical fibroblasts were integrated within an ECM-simulating hydrogel in a tailored, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-free microfluidic platform. To demonstrate the utility of our newly devised model for drug testing, we employed the widely used chemotherapeutic agent cisplatin, successfully demonstrating a response to very low, patient-relevant concentrations. Furthermore, donor-derived, PMNs perfused through the vasculature-like channels were recruited into the tissue and retained their capacity for NETosis, illustrating the model's ability to capture and study intricate immune responses.

2. Results

2.1. Tailored Microphysiological Platform for Cervical Cancer Tissue Models

The novel microphysiological platform was designed specifically for the generation and cultivation of cancerous cervical tissues with the capability of recreating dynamic flow and perfusion of immune cells. The PDMS-free cervical cancer-on-chip (CCoC) platform is based on thermoplastic microfluidic modules incorporating two separate channel systems on a standard microscope slide footprint (Figure 1A). Each individual system comprises a straight channel that is separated by a porous membrane (pore size: 5 μm) from four cylindrical, open-top tissue compartments. The modules consist of a stack of three polymer layers sandwiching a laser-cut polyethylene terephthalate (PET) membrane. The channel layer is patterned in a styrene ethylene butylene styrene (SEBS)/polycarbonate (PC) hybrid material via a combined hot embossing and thermal fusion process (Figure 1B). The microchannels (300 μm wide and 200 μm high) are, thereby, structured in the thermoplastic elastomer SEBS, while the thermoplastic PC bottom layer provides mechanical reinforcement for easier handling and enhances optical properties.^[52] The hybrid channel layer is fused to a SEBS tissue layer and a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) reservoir layer via a thermal bonding process, whereby the PET membrane is sandwiched between channel and tissue layers (Figure 1C). In both tissue and reservoir layer, cylindrical through-holes (diameter 1.5 and 5 mm, respectively) are patterned via laser structuring to generate an open-top cavity. This cavity consists of a tissue well and a media reservoir that allows submersed culture of the tissue and can be sealed during culture. The ports in the reservoir layer are connected to the channel in the media layer and hold adapters for the connection with tubing to the syringe pump or immune cell reservoirs. An essential aspect of the hybrid-material platform is its capability to utilize a biopsy punch to extract tissues for subsequent analyses, allowing for diverse readouts from a single system (Figure 1D). The biopsy punch is small enough to pass through the larger hole

of the thermoplastic reservoir layer while maintaining a protective ring of thermoplastic elastomer around the fragile tissue.

2.2. Isolation of Human Donor-Derived Peripheral Neutrophils and Cervical Fibroblasts

To recreate the *in vivo* TME and enable future studies on patient-specific effects, PMNs, and primary cervical fibroblasts were isolated from human, donor-derived biopsies by adapting existing protocols.^[53,54] Flow cytometry analysis revealed high purity of PMNs isolated from whole blood, with 84.7% of the CD45+ positive population being positive for CD11b+, 93.4% for CD16+, 92.3% for CD66b+, and 84.6% for all CD11b+CD16+CD66b+ (Figure 2A). Cervical fibroblasts were isolated from the subepithelial stroma of cervical tissue biopsies from otherwise indicated surgical tissue removal (e. g. uterus descensus) using specifically tailored protocols and expressed fibroblast-associated vimentin and fibronectin in subsequent expansion culture (Figure 2B).

2.3. On-Chip Generation of a Human 3D Cervical Cancer Tissue

In cervical cancer, epithelial cells cross the basal lamina and form cancerous nests (Figure S2A, Supporting Information) in the stroma featuring fibroblasts as the most abundant cell type of the TME. On-chip, we emulated cancerous nests by integrating cancer cell aggregates into the 3D stromal tissue. These aggregates recapitulate a pathophysiological architecture of solid tumors with resulting internal gradients reminiscent of tumors, including decreasing levels of nutrients, oxygen, pH, and drugs toward their core, along with an accumulation of metabolites amongst others (Figure 3B).^[55,56] Cancer cell aggregates were generated in agarose μ -wells via forced cell aggregation of SiHa cells, an established cell line from a squamous carcinoma grade II.^[57] While forming looser aggregates than, for instance, fibroblasts (Figure 3A and Figure S3, Supporting Information), SiHa could be seeded as aggregates on-chip, replicating multicellular cancerous nests as present in *in vivo* cervical tumors. To model cervical cancer and aspects of the TME, SiHa aggregates (100 000 per mL) were embedded together with cervical fibroblasts (10e6 per mL, based on preliminary test with collagen hydrogels, Figure S2, Supporting Information) in a dextran hydrogel in the tissue chambers of the microfluidic platform (Figure 3B). The chemically defined dextran hydrogel contains covalently attached RGD peptides to promote cell adhesion and a cell-degradable peptide in the hyaluronic acid-based crosslinker, which can be targeted by the human cervical fibroblasts expressing MMP1 and 3.^[58] To culture the cancerous tissue, chemically defined media FTAL5 containing no components of animal or human origin was employed. A continuous supply of FTAL5 at a rate of 20 $\mu\text{L h}^{-1}$ was maintained through the channel to deliver nutrients to the cancerous tissue and remove metabolites from it. A reservoir well above the tissue contained 50 μL of media, maintaining a moist environment that was preserved in sterile conditions using a sealing membrane. The successful formation of a 3D tissue mimicking the physiological architecture was evaluated after 14 days of on-chip culture via immunofluorescence

Figure 1. Design and fabrication of the microfluidic platform: A) Schematic and photograph of the microscope-slide sized PDMS-free platform incorporating two independent microfluidic systems, each supplying four open-top tissue compartments consisting of a cylindrical tissue well positioned between a porous membrane and a reservoir. B) The channel layer is patterned in a SEBS/PC hybrid material via a combined hot embossing and thermal fusion process. C) Subsequently, laser-structured PET-membranes, SEBS tissue, and PMMA reservoir layers are fused to the membrane/bottom layer via thermal bonding. D) The hybrid-material platform allows for tissue retrieval with a biopsy punch, providing the opportunity to apply different readout methods on the same system. SEBS: styrene ethylene butylene styrene, PC: polycarbonate, PET: polyethylene terephthalate, PMMA: poly(methyl methacrylate).

Figure 2. Isolation of human donor-derived peripheral PMNs and cervical fibroblasts: A) Peripheral PMNs were isolated from human whole blood of three donors, separating peripheral blood mononucleated cells (PBMCs) using density gradients, and their purity was assessed via flow cytometry measurements. B) Cervical stromal layers were separated from epithelium and connective tissue and fibroblasts were subsequently isolated and characterized by vimentin (vim) and fibronectin (FN) immunofluorescence staining.

staining with cell type-specific cytokeratin and vimentin markers (Figure 3C). The dextran hydrogel demonstrated good stability without shrinkage and provided a robust 3D matrix for the cells. SiHa spheroids were distributed in the tissue as cancerous nests, with a more defined and compact spheroid-appearance after 3 days of on-chip cultivation in dextran (Figure S4, Supporting Information), as opposed to their loose appearance at the timepoint of seeding (Figure 3A). Fibroblasts were dispersed in-between the μ -tumors. Life/dead staining revealed a high level of tissue viability, with an increased number of dead cells in the center of large spheroids (Figure 3D).

2.4. Presence of Fibroblasts Impacts Cancer Cell Viability and Proliferation

The inclusion of fibroblasts in tumor models provides a more representative cellular context by considering the influence of fibroblast-mediated signaling in the TME, which can have an impact on overall pathogenesis as well as the efficacy and toxicity of therapeutics. To investigate how fibroblasts affect the viability and proliferation of μ -tumors in the cervix, we generated tissue-chips containing spheroids of either cancer cells or fibroblasts and cultured them in the presence or absence of single fibroblasts distributed in-between. In comparison to the tissues containing solely cancerous spheroids (SiHa sph), monocultures of primary cervical fibroblasts (F sph + F) exhibited a lower number of dead cells (Figure 4A). However, when fibroblasts were intro-

duced into the TME of SiHa spheroids (SiHa sph + F), the viability of cancer cell spheroids increased significantly as demonstrated via life/dead-stainings and quantification of LDH release in the perfused effluent (Figure 4B). Despite increased cell numbers in the co-culture condition, LDH release was significantly lower compared to the cancer spheroid mono-culture. Additionally, presence of fibroblasts in the tissue supported cancer growth as the spheroids grew larger and featured a higher expression of the proliferation marker Ki67 (Figure 4C).

2.5. Cervical Tissue Responds to Cisplatin Treatment at Patient-Relevant Doses

To demonstrate the applicability of the CCoC model for dynamic testing of cancer therapeutics, we exposed the model to the chemotherapeutic medication cisplatin, and mimicked clinically relevant treatment plans. Cisplatin is one of the most utilized therapeutic agents for addressing various solid cancers. Its anticancer effects rely on multiple mechanisms, with its primary accepted pathway involving the formation of DNA lesions through interactions with purine bases, subsequently triggering various signal transduction pathways leading to apoptosis. Nonetheless, the inherent challenges of cisplatin, encompassing side effects and drug resistance, curtail its applicability and therapeutic efficacy.^[59] For cervical cancer patients, a commonly accepted treatment plan involves weekly administration of 40 mg m^{-2} of cisplatin for 5–6 cycles alongside radiation therapy.^[60]

Figure 3. Tissue generation and characterization of the cervical cancer-on-chip: A) SiHa were seeded in μ -agarose wells, where SiHa formed loose aggregates after 24 h. B) Schematic cross-section illustrating the cancer tissue within the tissue well. Media is linearly perfused in the channel at a flow rate of $20 \mu\text{L h}^{-1}$. The local consumption of nutrients and oxygen by the cells and the continuous supply thereof results in the creation of gradients both within the tissue and within the spheroids. C) Fluorescence microscope image of the CCoc after 14 days of on-chip culture, showing single, primary fibroblasts (stained with vimentin-antibody, white) dispersed in between SiHa-spheroids (stained with cytokeratin-antibody, turquoise) in a 3D dextran hydrogel. D) Orthogonal view of confocal microscopy images of a CCoc after 2 weeks of on-chip culture stained with Calcein AM (living cells, green) and PI (dead, magenta), demonstrating high viability.

Figure 4. Cervical fibroblasts increase viability and proliferation of the cancerous tissue: A) SiHa and fibroblast spheroids respectively were cultured in the presence (SiHa sph + F or F sph + F) or absence (SiHa sph) of single fibroblasts for 14 days and stained for living (Calcein AM, green) and dead cells (propidium iodide, PI, magenta). Two systems were generated from the same donor and run in parallel to obtain duplicate wells for each condition. The presence of fibroblasts resulted in increased viability and size of SiHa spheroids as shown in the fluorescence images of the tissue on-chip. Brightfield (BF) images show densely packed tissues in all conditions, particularly when SiHa spheroids are present. Viability assessment via B) Calcein/PI staining and C) LDH release into the effluent from the cultures described in (A) demonstrates higher viability when SiHa-spheroids were co-cultured with fibroblasts compared to the mono-culture. Bars represent the mean \pm SD of two wells from two systems (Calcein/PI) and effluent from four systems (LDH) from the same donor run in parallel, each of which was measured in triplicates with the mean of each system shown as single dots. D) The same conditions as described in (A) were stained with the proliferation marker Ki67 (magenta), SiHa marker cytokeratin (turquoise), and fibroblast marker vimentin (white). The fluorescence microscopy images reveal boosted proliferation in the co-culture conditions.

When patients received cisplatin intravenously over 1 h, the cisplatin concentration in the serum reached its peak after 1 h at $c_{\max} = 5.37 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ($17.9 \mu\text{M}$), then decreased rapidly within 4 h to $C_{5h} = 1.73 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ($5.8 \mu\text{M}$).^[61] To simulate the treatment that a cervical tumor would experience in vivo, we leveraged the perfusion to generate different (dynamic) treatment regimes. In a constant “low” exposure condition, the tissue was treated with 80% of C_{5h} , that is, $1.4 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ($4.6 \mu\text{M}$) cisplatin for 24 h, whereby cisplatin delivery to the four wells occurred with small time differences (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Additionally, a “dynamic” treatment regimen was implemented, featuring an initial 1-h perfusion of cisplatin at 80% of c_{\max} , that is, $4.3 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ ($14.3 \mu\text{M}$), followed by a 23-h perfusion of cisplatin as in the “low” condition. These treatments were initiated 5 days after generating the μ -tissue on-chip and were repeated weekly (Figure 5A). The initial 24-h cisplatin treatment on day 5 and the repetition of the treatment on day 12, demonstrate an impact on cancer cell viability in the dynamic condition, while the constant low condition did not show significant effects (Figure 5B). To assess if the constant low condition will eventually also have an impact, we added a third treatment on day 19. After three cycles of repeated dosing, the constant low condition also exhibited a significant tumor-killing effect as demonstrated by LDH release and TUNEL staining (Figure 5C).

2.6. Neutrophils Are Recruited into the Cancerous Tissue and Are Capable of Producing NETs in the TME

Immune cells in the TME play a crucial role in influencing both pathogenesis and treatment outcomes. Ideally, an in vitro cancer model should integrate cancerous tissue within a 3D TME that includes vascular structures and immune components.^[62] Particularly of interest for cervical cancer are PMNs and their functional structures known as NETs. Hence, we aimed to investigate the amenability of the CCoC for perfusion and recruitment of functional PMNs into the tumor tissue.

To characterize functionality of the donor-derived PMNs, we assessed their capability to undergo NETosis off-chip—thereto, we treated PMNs immediately after isolation for 6 h with 100 nM phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) and subsequently stained for PMN and NETosis markers CD66b, MPO, NE and H3cit as well as nuclear stain Hoechst (Figure S6A, Supporting Information). Upon stimulation, we observed critical hallmarks of NETosis, which include extracellular DNA co-localized with neutrophil-derived proteins as well as H3cit expression.^[41] Without stimulation, intracellular MPO as well as net-like structures were observed, indicating spontaneous NETosis.^[63,64] Collectively, these results show PMA-induced formation of NETs by donor-derived PMNs in vitro. Next, we had to identify a media suitable for cervical (cancer) tissue culture that at the same time supports functionality of PMNs. Several media were screened for PMN viability and their ability to undergo NETosis, including RPMI, as the most commonly used medium for PMN culture,^[63,64] and FTAL5, as the medium previously used for on-chip cancerous tissue culture, as well as further media combinations previously shown to be compatible for the culture of healthy keratinocytes with fibroblasts as well as for the co-culture of microvascular endothelial cells and T cells (Figure S6B, Supporting

Information). While PMNs’ ability to undergo NETosis was diminished in the cervical co-culture media “PM + DMEM,” the SYTOX green assay demonstrated functional NETosis for FTAL5. Unstimulated cells featured high viability while PMA stimulation led to an increase in cell death after 2 h with further loss of viability until 6 h.

To mimic PMN circulation through and extravasation from the blood vessels of cancerous tissue, PMNs were added into tailored reservoirs in the inlet ports on day 3 of on-chip culture and perfused through the vasculature-like channels for 5 h (Figure 6A). PMNs, stained with a cell tracker prior to perfusion, attached to the membrane and could be observed actively migrating through the porous membrane to the μ -tumors and fibroblasts via real-time monitoring. The tissue displayed solely a few single dead cells, indicating high viability across all cell types. Since cell tracking does not provide sufficient information about cell type, CCoCs were stained for PMN markers CD66b and NE as well as T cell marker CD3 after perfusion with unstained PMNs over 5 days (Figure 6B). Contamination with T cells was minimal, and the majority of cells adhering to the membrane at the top of the channel and recruited to the cancerous tissue expressed PMN markers. After PMN-perfusion, the NETosis inducer PMA was introduced for an additional 5 h. While some spontaneous NETosis occurred in both the tissue and in the channel, the addition of PMA strongly increased the formation of NETs in both compartments, as shown with the NETosis markers MPO (Figure 6C; secondary antibody control in Figure S7, Supporting Information).

3. Discussion

To tackle one of the most pressing women’s health-related pathologies, cervical cancer, a leading cause of cancer-related deaths in women, there is an urgent need for physiological model systems with human relevance and predictive value. In this study, we leverage organ-on-chip technology to generate a model that integrates cervical cancer, aspects of the TME as well as vasculature-like perfusion. We introduce a novel open-top microfluidic platform tailored to recreate immunocompetent cervical cancer tissue based on patient-specific primary cells and tumor spheroids and demonstrate its applicability for chemotherapy assessment and immune cell perfusion.

3.1. A Novel PDMS-Free Microfluidic Platform Amenable for Tissue Retrieval

The open-top design of the platform offers direct access to the tissue, facilitating tissue generation and retrieval as well as microscopy. By utilizing thermoplastic materials instead of the commonly used PDMS, we circumvent challenges arising from strong absorption of small hydrophobic molecules; an aspect that is particularly important for women’s health-related cancer models, where a controlled exposure to hormones and drugs that are often strongly hydrophobic could be required in future applications. This is exemplified by metastasis-inducing effects of estradiol (E2), which was demonstrated in the context of PMN in a breast cancer model.^[65] The combination of thermoplastic elastomers and thermoplastics combines the benefits of both

materials, that is, stability and optical accessibility as well as amenability for extraction of tissue using a biopsy punch. The latter provides a significant benefit for downstream analysis—retrieval of tissues enables easier and independent analysis of each of the four tissues per chip and improves compatibility with standard cell/tissue culture readout routines, for instance, immunohistochemistry, high-resolution microscopy, and gene expression analysis. The small adapters in the ports allow for flexible connection of tubing and (immune cell) reservoirs. The use of larger media reservoirs proves advantageous for cultivating the tissue, whereas cannulas with short needles as immune cell reservoirs reduce dead volume and ensure facile incorporation of immune cells into the perfusion. Although we focused on user-friendliness, scalability of fabrication processes, and compatibility with standard equipment,^[66] the general limitation of organ-on-chip experimentation being more complex than conventional cell culture or Transwell assays and requiring specialized training also holds true for the CCoC platform.^[67]

3.2. Microscale Open-Top Tissue Chambers Enable Facile 3D Tissue Generation and Integration of Patient-Derived Cells

The small cultivation area of the CCoC is particularly well-suited for the integration of primary cells, as the cell numbers per biopsy are often limited. Thereby, a large number of individual tissue models can be generated from a single donor, allowing to assess many different conditions for the same patient circumventing donor-to-donor heterogeneity. In this study, we derived primary cervical fibroblasts and PMNs from healthy donors, not only providing human and tissue-specific genetic background, but also allowing, for instance, the study of interindividual differences in NET formation propensity. Cultivating primary cervical cancer cells and patient-derived organoids has proven to be challenging with only a few examples reported to date.^[49] Especially organoids from squamous cervical cancer have been rarely reported and demonstrated very low success rates for organoid generation of 22.2% and 50%.^[68,69] In contrast, a total of at least 52 cervical cancer cell lines have been established, substantially contributing to the advancement of our knowledge and comprehension of cervical cancer pathogenesis and treatment.^[70] To generate cervical carcinoma tissue, we utilized the squamous cervical cancer cell line SiHa, as it represents the most common type of cervical cancer. To recapitulate cell-cell interactions in tumors, the 3D architecture featuring internal gradients of nutrients, oxygen, and signaling factors as well as the drug penetration reminiscent of tumors, 3D spheroids provide a much better approach than single cells or 2D culture and more closely resemble *in vivo* tumor

conditions.^[62,71] In the future, the model could be further refined and advanced to fully patient-specific models by integrating cervical cancer organoids instead of SiHa spheroids and by adding further components of the TME such as tissue infiltrating lymphocytes.

3.3. Dynamic Monitoring of Tissue Structure and Function on-Chip

To assess structural and functional hallmarks of the tissues in the CCoC, we focused primarily on immunofluorescence microscopy as well as effluent analysis, since thereby structural information is maintained, and non-invasive dynamic monitoring enabled. The compatibility of the CCoC with non-invasive live-cell imaging in combination with long-term culture is a powerful tool, in particular when real-time measurements are combined with fluorescent labeling such as cell-trackers, conjugated antibodies, and viability dyes. Confocal microscopy enables imaging up to $\approx 200 \mu\text{m}$ into the tissue ensuring direct structural and functional assessment of a large portion of the 3D model, especially when paired with immunofluorescence staining. In the future, it would be intriguing to employ tissue-clearing techniques to obtain a comprehensive view of the tissue. Constant perfusion of the microfluidic platform allows continuous collection of effluent, providing an additional time-resolved non-invasive method for the dynamic assessment of tissue function and cellular interactions. The analysis of effluents can be performed using many widely available, cost-effective standard readout methods employed in traditional 2D cell cultures, thus expanding the scope of readout options. In this study, we monitored the release of LDH from the tissues into the effluent over a 24-h period; if desired, much higher time resolution could be achieved. Effluent analyses can be further resorted to for a thorough investigation of biochemical factors such as chemokines and cytokines or clinically relevant biomarkers, e. g. the analysis of NET markers, which play an increasingly important role for cancer patients' diagnosis and management.^[45,72]

3.4. Challenges and Opportunities of Long-Term Culture of Complex Multi-Cell-Type Tissues

Long-term culture of cancerous tissue allows for prolonged observation of tumor progression to better understand the underlying mechanisms and factors that contribute to cancer development and metastasis. Through this extended culture time, a deeper understanding of the complex interactions between cancer cells, stromal components, and the surrounding

Figure 5. Cervical cancer models respond to cisplatin treatment: A) Timeline employed for cisplatin treatment: 5 days post tissue-generation, CCoCs were exposed for 24 h to either a “low” dose of cisplatin at $4.6 \mu\text{M}$, or a “dynamic” treatment with an initial 1 h perfusion of $14.3 \mu\text{M}$ cisplatin (CDDP) followed by 23 h of “low” dose, emulating cisplatin dynamics in patient's blood after intravenous application. Treatment was administered weekly, recapitulating the accepted treatment plan for cervical cancer patients. B) LDH release in perfused effluents from treated as well as untreated CCoCs and hydrogel-only chips were analyzed on days 6, 13, and 20. The initial treatment as well as the second treatment showed significant effects in the dynamic condition. After three treatments, the “low” dose condition also showed a significant effect on viability. Bars represent the mean \pm SD; 4 independent systems for the untreated and low condition, 3 for the dynamic condition, and 2 for the hydrogel-only condition; all replicate systems were generated from the same donor, run in parallel, and measured in triplicates. C) Cell death upon cisplatin treatment was detected using a TUNEL assay (magenta) on d6 and d20 in experiments run sequentially from the same donor. Fluorescence microscopy images reveal minimal cytotoxic effects of the first treatment in all conditions and substantial cell death in the low condition after the third treatment. Brightfield images display tissue growth from day 6 into a densely packed tissue after 20 days of culture, with reduced density upon cell killing with triton (dead) or repeated cisplatin treatment.

microenvironment can be obtained. After 2 weeks of culture, we evaluated the tissue's viability and observed an overall high viability. In larger spheroids, dead cells were predominantly located in the center, resembling necrotic areas observed *in vivo* within cancerous nests.^[73] The different sizes of spheroids provide a good replication of the size heterogeneity seen in neoplastic clusters in patients. To assess the effects of stromal cell types in the TME, we integrated fibroblasts and observed improved viability and faster growth in the tumor spheroids. These findings suggest paracrine cell-cell communication between cancer cells and fibroblasts. Several studies previously reported two-way communication between cervical cancer cells and fibroblasts, with numerous pro-tumoral effects summarized and reviewed by Villegas-Pineda et al. and Spurgeon & Lambert.^[13,74] Transforming growth factor-beta (TGF β), for instance, has been shown to play an important role in the interaction of CAFs with CaSki and HeLa, contributing to increased proliferation and decreased apoptosis.^[75,76] *In vivo*, the growth of cervical cancer cells HeLa and CaSki was enhanced when injected in mice as co-culture with CAFs.^[77] Liang and colleagues, moreover, reported that SiHa cells secrete Wnt2B exosomes, which enhanced CAF markers alpha smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) and fibroblast activation protein (FAP) within 2 days and promoted tumor growth, suggesting a positive feedback loop for SiHa's own growth stimulation.^[78] Hence, our data showing fibroblasts enhancing the viability and proliferation of cervical cancerous tissue aligns with the pro-tumoral effects of CAFs reported in cervical cancer. In future studies, the model could be employed to study fibroblast plasticity and assess CAF-marker expression in the CCoCs, including α -SMA and FAP,^[76,78,79] as well as TGF β in the effluent.

Immune components of the TME tremendously influence disease progression and treatment outcomes. Being able to integrate aspects of the immune system constitutes a powerful opportunity for organ-on-chip technology, particularly for cancer-on-chip models.^[80] PMNs are not only the most abundant circulating leukocyte, but play an important role in tumors, where they can have tumor-antagonizing and -promoting functions. In cervical cancer, TANs are prognostically significant and considered a potential therapeutic target.^[38] As the number of cellular components within the tissue increased, we identified a suitable media that would maintain cellular viability and functionality of all cell types. We investigated the NETotic capacity of PMNs in media used for the culture of cervical tissues as well as microvascular endothelial and immune cells. While some media revealed high spontaneous NETosis or prevented PMA-induced NET-formation, PMNs in FTAL5 displayed high NETotic capacity upon PMA stimulation and high viability with low spontaneous NETosis in the control. When PMNs were perfused through the microvasculature-like channels of the CCoC, adherence to the

membrane and recruitment into the tissue could be observed. We confirmed viability as well as cell identity of PMNs on-chip. When NETosis was induced with PMA, critical events of NET formation on-chip could be replicated. In future studies, further investigations could elucidate if NET formation can also be induced by cancer cells directly, as has been shown by several aggressive cancer cells with tumor-derived interleukin 8 (IL-8) and granulocyte colony-stimulating factor (G-CSF) potentially playing critical roles.^[25] NETs have been found in cervical cancer,^[39] however, it is not yet known whether NETs are induced by cervical cancer cells directly. Also, the model could be employed to examine the effects of the co-culture on NETosis, as it has been shown that CAFs can induce NETs in mice.^[81] Hence, the immunocompetent CCoC can aid further mechanistic investigations into the role of NETosis in cancer and its TME and potentially test (immune)therapeutic options and combinations.

3.5. Monitoring Drug Responses Using Clinically-Relevant Treatment Regimens

In vitro compound testing performed at concentrations much higher than the plasma peak concentrations in humans (up to 20–200 \times), raises the question of whether such high concentrations are relevant in predicting response in human physiology.^[82,83] In previous studies, SiHa spheroids were treated with cisplatin at 20–334 μ M for 3 days, 5.5–88 μ M for 2 days, or 10–100 μ M for 1–2 days.^[84–86] Choice of these concentrations and durations, far above clinical treatment regimes, is often driven by short culture durations and limitations of static well plate culture. We leveraged the capability for long-term culture and perfusion of the CCoC and employed repeated dosing in clinically relevant drug delivery routes, schedules, and concentrations. Specifically, we applied a dynamic condition that mimics *in vivo* plasma concentrations during 24 h treatment windows in a discretized form by applying a concentration of 80% of c_{\max} during the initial hour and 80% of C_{5h} for the remaining 23 h. While we used significantly lower concentrations than previous *in vitro* studies, the dynamic treatment exhibited significant tumor killing already after the first treatment whereas the constant low condition required three cycles of treatment. This demonstrates on the one hand the potential and the impact provided by the organ-on-chip technology's capability for dynamic concentration profiles but also the necessity to carefully choose clinically relevant dynamic treatment profiles in order to generate predictive and translatable data. For future studies, comparing these outcomes with cisplatin-sensitive cell lines such as CC7 or CC10^[87] or patient-specific cervical cancer organoids^[68,69,88] would be compelling and the approach could potentially be utilized to provide patient-specific dosing recommendations and minimum effective dosing

Figure 6. PMN Recruitment and NETosis in the CCoC: A) Schematic cross-section of the CCoC perfused with PMNs via the microvasculature-like channel (center). PMNs were labeled with a cell tracker (magenta) and perfusion (left panel) as well as recruitment into the cancerous tissue (right panel) were observed via live-cell imaging with a fluorescent microscope. PMNs (magenta), SiHa (green), and fibroblasts (blue) displayed high viability, evidenced by the minimal number of SYTOX (yellow) positive cells. B) Fluorescence microscopy images of PMN marker CD66b (yellow) and NE (red) as well as T cell marker CD3 (turquoise) confirm the high purity of PMNs. PMN adhered to the membrane and a subset of cells was recruited into the cancerous 3D tissue. C) Following 5 h of PMN-perfusion and exposure to PMA for another 5 h, tissues were stained with CD66b (yellow), NE (red), MPO (turquoise), and H3cit (magenta). Fluorescence microscopy images revealed spotty spontaneous NETosis in the CCoC without stimulation, while PMA-stimulated NETosis was evident as large MPO-positive structures (turquoise) in both tissue and channel.

estimations. However, this will require much more comprehensive testing and benchmarking using sets of established and experimental compounds not limited to small molecules and also including immunomodulatory drugs.^[89]

4. Conclusion

We present a novel PDMS-free microfluidic platform tailored for the generation and cultivation of cervical cancerous tissue. The platform is amenable for real-time monitoring and tissue retrieval to employ various readouts from the same chip. The microscale open-top tissue chambers enable facile generation and long-term culture of SiHa spheroids embedded in a stroma containing donor-derived cervical fibroblasts. The 3D tissue recapitulates physiological architecture and cell–cell interactions within the TME, resulting in enhanced tumor viability and growth in the presence of cervical fibroblasts. The tissue structure and function were monitored via (live-cell) immunofluorescence microscopy and effluent analysis. As a proof-of-concept for the applicability of the CCoC for drug testing, response of the CCoC to cisplatin treatments at clinically-relevant treatment regimes, schedules, and routes of administration was assessed. Furthermore, PMNs were recruited into the tissue from the microvasculature-like channel, while retaining NETotic functionality. Taken together, we leveraged organ-on-chip technology to develop a novel open-top microfluidic platform, designed to replicate immunocompetent cervical (cancer) tissue using patient-specific primary cells and tumor spheroids. We also showcase its potential for evaluating chemotherapy and simulating immune cell perfusion.

5. Experimental Section

Design and Layer Preparation: The design of the microfluidic platform was created using AUTODESK AUTOCAD 2021. To fabricate the platforms multiple different types of polymer sheets (5 mm thick sheets of PMMA (Modulor, Germany) for the media reservoir layers, 750 μm thick sheets of SEBS (Hexpol TPE AB, Sweden) for the tissue layers, and PET membranes with a pore size of 5 μm (Sabeu, Germany)) were processed utilizing laser-assisted structuring (Laser Cutter R5000 V1.0, Universal Laser Systems, USA). The dimensions and different views of the layers are depicted in Figure S1A–C, Supporting Information.

The bottom layers containing the media channels were structured in a SEBS/PC (It4ip, Belgium) hybrid via hot-embossing, whereby molds were produced based on previously introduced protocols,^[52] with minor adaptations—an SU-8 master mold was produced from a 4-inch silicon wafer (Siegert Wafer, Germany) via SU-8 50 (Kayaku Advanced Materials, Inc., Germany) based UV-lithography using patterned photomasks (KOPP-Desktopmedia, Germany) in an MA6 mask aligner (SÜSS Micro Tec, Germany) and mrDev 600 developer (MicroChemicals GmbH, Germany). A PDMS mold was subsequently fabricated by pouring a PDMS pre-polymer (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning, Germany) on the silicon mold, which was placed in a large circular petri dish, cured for 24 h at room temperature (RT) and afterward for 24 h at 80 °C. The resulting PDMS mold was placed into a custom-built steel tool and a two-component, high-temperature stable epoxy resin (EpoxAcast 670 HT, USA) was applied. The tool was left under vacuum for 24 h at RT and placed into an oven at 60 °C for 24 h, after which the mold could be removed from the tool. Subsequently, the mold was placed at 80 °C for 2 h, followed by 3 h at 130 °C. The mold was then gently cooled overnight by turning off the oven and opening the air vents.

The molds were employed for hot embossing the media channel structure into the thermoplastic elastomer SEBS and simultaneous fusion of

SEBS to PC. Thereto, 11 \times 11 cm pieces of SEBS (250 μm thickness) and PC (175 μm thickness) were placed onto the mold and the polymer layers were pressed by a laminar roller. The construct was then flipped and placed onto a mirror-polished stainless-steel plate (TGA, Germany), which was spray-coated with a mold release agent (Weicon, Germany) beforehand. This construct was then placed into a 130 °C preheated hot press (LabEcon 100, Fontijne, Netherlands). The mold was pressed with 6 kN at 130 °C for 10 min to structure the SEBS layer and bond it to the PC layer. The resulting SEBS/PC media layer was then assembled with the other chip parts.

Chip Assembly with Adapter Integration: The SEBS tissue layer was aligned and assembled onto the PMMA media reservoir layer. The PET membranes were cleaned by submersion into isopropanol (MIPU1025, MicroChemicals), dried for 30 s, and placed over the tissue holes. Subsequently, the SEBS/PC bottom layers were placed on top and aligned with the other layers. The stack of polymer layers was placed between two clean glass slides (Menzel, Germany) and sandwiched between two metal plates (each 700 g) pre-heated to 60 °C. The platform was subsequently thermally bonded at 80 °C in an oven (Memmert, Germany) for at least 12 h. The pressure on the chips equaled \approx 3.9, 1.9, and 1.3 kPa for one, two, and three chips, respectively. Tubing adapters were prepared by inserting a cannula (5 mm in length, outer diameter of 0.6 mm) derived from stainless steel plastic hub dispensing needles (Gauge 23, KDS2312P, Weller) into flexible plastic tubing (length \approx 8 mm, inner diameter of 0.5 mm, AAD04103, VWR). The adapters were inserted with the tubing ahead into the in- and outlet ports of the chip. PDMS was applied at the interface between adapter and chip and cured for 1–2 h at 80 °C, sealing and stabilizing the connection. The platform was sterilized with EtOH (70%), washed with DI water, air-dried, and equilibrated in the incubator before cell seeding.

Cell Isolation and Culture: Human biopsies of the cervix uteri and whole blood were obtained from patients with unrelated diseases and healthy donors, respectively. Patients and donors gave informed consent as approved by the ethical committee of the Eberhard Karls University Tübingen (No. 495/2018/BO02 for the isolation of fibroblasts from cervix uteri and PBMCs and PMNs from whole blood).

The isolation process for primary human cervical fibroblasts was adapted from Deng et al. with minor modifications.^[53] Immediately after surgery and gross examination by the pathologist, biopsies were washed three times in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, D8537, Sigma Aldrich) supplemented with penicillin-streptomycin (P/S, 100 U mL^{-1} and 100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, P06-07100, Pan Biotech). Excess connective tissue was removed and remaining epithelium with subepithelial stromal layer was cut into small stripes and digested overnight in dispase II (2 U mL^{-1} , 17105041, Gibco) in DMEM/F12 (12634010, Gibco) at 4 °C. Epithelia were removed and stromal layer was minced into small pieces of \approx 2 \times 2 mm and further digested with collagenase I (1 U Wuensch mL^{-1} , C1-22, Sigma Aldrich) in DMEM (41965039, Gibco) for 90 min at 37 °C on a rocker (Rocker 2D, IKA, Germany). Cell suspension was filtered through a 70 μm strainer (542170, Greiner Bio-one, Germany) and mixed with DMEM with fetal calve serum (FCS, 10%, SH30066.03, Cytavia). After an additional wash of the strainer with PBS, the cell suspension was centrifuged at 200 \times g for 5 min and plated in DMEM with FCS (10%). Cells were incubated at 37 °C with 5% CO_2 in a humidified atmosphere. Media was changed every 2–3 days and TrypLE Select (12563-029, Gibco) was used for detachment.

SiHa were provided by T. Iftner and F. Stubenrauch (Eberhard Karls University Tübingen, Germany) and cultured as described for primary cervical fibroblasts.

The procedure for isolating PMNs from whole blood was based on a previously published protocol, with minor adjustments.^[54] Whole blood was collected in ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) monovettes (02.1066.001, Sarstedt) and immediately diluted with the same volume of 2% dextran buffer (4.01 g mL^{-1} dextran (31392, Sigma Aldrich, Germany), 0.9 g mL^{-1} NaCl (A2942, AppliChem, Germany), in sterile water) and incubated for 10 min at RT. The supernatant was layered on top of Histopaque-107 separation medium for density gradient centrifugation (10771, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) in a ratio of 2:3 [v/v]. Samples were centrifuged at 400 \times g for 30 min without breaks and acceleration for experiments in 2D and 800 \times g for 20 min with acceleration at running profile 4 for chip perfusion.

Blood plasma and separation medium were discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in erythrocyte lysis buffer (PL-29-L, C.C. Pro, Germany) and incubated for 5 min at RT. PBS was added to reduce osmotic pressure and cell suspension was centrifuged at $200 \times g$ for 5 min with maximum acceleration and deceleration. Supernatant was discarded and the pellet was resuspended in the desired medium or PBS.

Spheroid Generation: Spheroids were formed as described previously.^[90] In brief, wells of a 6-well microwell culture plate (AggreWell400, STEMCELL Technologies, USA) were replicated out of Hydrosil (101301, SILADENT, Germany) and glued to a PMMA holder. After sterilization with 70% EtOH, the structured side was remolded with agarose (3%) and transferred to a 24 well-plate, with the microwells pointing upward. DMEM with FCS (10%) was added before removal of air bubbles. Cervical fibroblasts or SiHa were detached with TrypLE, centrifuged at $200 \times g$ for 5 min, and resuspended in DMEM with FCS (10%). 480 000 cells were seeded into each well and were centrifuged at $200 \times g$ for 5 min and incubated at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere until use the next day.

Cell Seeding in Dextran-Hydrogel: The next day, 3-D Life RGD peptide (0.5 mm, Acetyl-Cys-Doa*-Doa-Gly-Arg-Gly-Asp-Ser-Pro-NH₂; Doa = 8-amino-3,6-dioxaoctanoic acid, P10-3, Cellendes, Germany) was chemically crosslinked to 3-D Life SG-dextran (2.9 mm, M91-3, Cellendes, Germany) according to manufacturer's instructions. Spheroids were harvested by transferring them with a P1000 to a 5 mL Eppendorf tube and left to sediment by gravity.

Spheroids (final 100 000 spheroids per mL) and cervical fibroblasts (final 10e6 fibroblasts per mL) were mixed in dextran hydrogel and crosslinked with thiol-functionalized hyaluronic acid crosslinker CD-HyLink (2.4 mm, Cellendes, Germany), containing the metalloprotease (MMP)-cleavable peptide (Pro-Leu-Gly-Leu-Trp-Ala). 1.5 µL of this mix was seeded in each well of the CCoC and 50 µL of CnT-Prime Full Thickness 3D Airlift Medium (FTAL5, CELLnTEC, Switzerland) was added into each reservoir. CCoC was sealed with Breath-Easy sealing membrane (Z380059, Sigma Aldrich) to reduce evaporation and keep a sterile environment.

Perfusion of the CCoC: Medical Tygon tubing (AAD04103, VWR, USA) was connected to the adapters at the ports. The tubing from the outlet led to reaction tubes as effluent collecting containers and the tubing into the inlet was connected to a syringe via a stainless-steel plastic hub dispensing needle (KDS2112P, Gauge 21, Weller, Germany). Media perfusion through the channel with FTAL5 was realized by pushing 20 µL h⁻¹ with an external syringe pumping system (LA-190, Landgraf Laborsysteme HLL GmbH, Germany).

PMN Perfusion: Tygon tubing was disconnected from the adapter and the cannula was removed. G23 Gauge dispensing needles were shortened to ≈8 mm length and inserted into the adapter as PMN reservoirs. PMNs were perfused for 5 h by withdrawing with 40 µL h⁻¹. Lids prepared from reaction tubes were added to maintain a sterile environment while allowing convenient refilling of the reservoirs.

Cisplatin Treatment: To investigate the effect of cisplatin on the viability of the CCoC, cisplatin (232120, Sigma Aldrich) was prepared as a stock (1.67 mM) in 0.9% saline and stored at 4 °C. 5 days post tissue-generation, cisplatin was perfused for 24 h as either a "low" dose of cisplatin at 4.6 µM in FTAL5, or a "dynamic" treatment with an initial 1 h perfusion of 14.3 µM cisplatin followed by 23 h of "low" dose. When CCoCs were treated repeatedly, FTAL5 without cisplatin was used for on-chip culture in-between treatments.^{5.5. Cell and tissue characterization}

Tissue Retrieval: For independent analysis of each tissue of the CCoC platform, tissue was retrieved using a 4 mm biopsy punch (49401, pfm medical AG) without the plunger. Thereby, tissue including a protective ring of SEBS material around it could be transferred from the biopsy punch using a knee bent tweezer (PZ31, Hartenstein) to 96 well plates for further analysis.

Flow Cytometry: To characterize PMNs isolated from whole blood, 500 000 cells were washed twice with PBS (300 rpm, 5 min at 4 °C) and resuspended in staining buffer (PBS with 10% FCS, 2 mM EDTA). For each panel, unstained cells were prepared as control. Cells were resuspended in Fc blocking solution (20 µg mL⁻¹, 564219, BD Pharmingen) and incubated for 20 min at RT. After washing, cells were incubated with Zombie Aqua for

Table 1. Conjugated antibodies for characterization of PMNs in flow cytometry measurements.

Antibody	Host species	Supplier	Catalog no.
CD45-AF700	Mouse	BioLegend	304024
CD66b-APC, REAfinity	Mouse	Miltenyi Biotec	130-117-692
CD11b-PE-Cy7	Mouse	BioLegend	301321
CD16-BV605	Mouse	BioLegend	302040

15 min at RT and subsequently stained with an antibody cocktail (Table 1) for 30 min at 4 °C in the dark. Cells were fixed in Fixation Buffer (88-8824, eBioscience, Thermo Fisher Scientific) for a minimum of 20 min at RT, resuspended in Permeabilization Buffer (88-8824, eBioscience, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and incubated with intracellular antibody cocktail for a minimum of 30 min at RT. Cells were washed and resuspended in staining buffer and measured with BD LSRFortessa flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, USA). Data was analyzed using FlowJo software.

Live/Dead Staining: Samples were stained after tissue retrieval in a 96 well plate. Calcein AM green (2 µg mL⁻¹, C3099, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was added for staining viable cells in PBS and incubated at 37 °C for 20 min. Propidium iodide (50 µg mL⁻¹, P4170, Sigma Aldrich) was added for 5 min at 37 °C for labeling nuclei of dead cells. Samples were washed with PBS containing magnesium chloride and calcium chloride (PBS+, D8662, Sigma Aldrich) for 10 min and imaged via fluorescence microscopy.

Sytox Green Assay: The method was adapted from Linnemann et al.^[91] In brief, 62 500 PMNs per cm² were seeded in a 96 well plate in respective media with SYTOX green (1 µM, S7020, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and PMN stimulation was performed with Phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA, 100 nM, ab120297, Abcam). Cells were lysed with 1% triton-X-100 (X100, Sigma Aldrich) as a reference for the maximum of dead cells. Fluorescence intensities were measured every hour using the Tristar 5 plate reader (Berthold, Germany) at 488 nm excitation and 523 nm emission. The fluorescence values of each replicate were normalized to the mean fluorescence intensity of triton X-100 lysed cells and multiplied by 100. The following media were tested: RPMI (21875, Gibco); RPMI with FCS (5%, SH30066, Cytavia); FTAL5, FTAL5 with FCS (5%), endothelial cell growth medium (ECGM, C-22010, PromoCell) supplemented with FCS (5%), endothelial cell growth supplement (ECGS, 12 µg mL⁻¹, C-39210, PromoCell), epidermal growth factor (0.1 µg mL⁻¹, EGF, C-39210, Promocell), FGF (1 ng mL⁻¹) and heparin (90 µg mL⁻¹, all C-39210; PromoCell); RPMI and ECGM mixed 1:1 [v/v]; and proliferation media (PM, advanced DMEM/F12 (P04-41150, PAN-Biotech) supplemented with B27 (1%, 17504-044, Life Technologies), EGF (10 ng mL⁻¹, C-39210; PromoCell), fibroblast growth factor (FGF, 100 ng mL⁻¹, C-39210, PromoCell), forskolin (10 µM, 1099, Tocris), glutamax (1%, 35050061, Thermo Fisher Scientific), HEPES (12 mM, 15630056, Thermo Fisher Scientific), hydrocortisone (0.5 µg mL⁻¹, H0888, Sigma Aldrich), N-2 supplement (1%, 07152, STEMCELL Technologies), N-acetyl-L-cysteine (1.25 mM, A9165, Sigma Aldrich), nicotinamide (10 mM, N0636, Merck), noggin (100 ng mL⁻¹, 120-10C, Peprotech), ROCK inhibitor (10 µM, 72304, STEMCELL Technologies), TGFB-kinase inhibitor IV (2 µM, 1614, Tocris)) mixed 1:1 [v/v] with DMEM (41965039, Gibco).

TUNEL Assay: Apoptotic cells were detected with the Click-iT Plus TUNEL Assay Kits for In Situ Apoptosis Detection (C10619, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Incubation times were increased as follows: samples were fixed for 30 min, permeabilized for 40 min, TdT reaction buffer incubated for 20–30 min, TdT reaction mix incubated between 2 h and overnight, washed three times for 30–90 min, the reaction cocktail incubated for 1–2.5 h, and was washed three times for 30–60 min. For a positive dead control, samples were perfused for 24 h with 1% triton-100 on day 5–6 or incubated statically for 4 h on day 20.

LDH Assay: Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)-release into the media was detected according to the manufacturer's instructions using the LDH-Glo Cytotoxicity Assay kit (J2381, Promega). Effluents were diluted 1:10 in

Table 2. Primary antibodies for immunofluorescent stainings.

Primary/conjugate antibody	Figure	Dilution, primary/conjugated antibody	Supplier, catalog number	Secondary antibody	Dilution, secondary antibody	Supplier, catalog number
CD3	6B	1:50, 4 °C for 2 days	Abcam, ab135372	Goat anti-rabbit—Alexa Fluor 488	1:100, 6 h at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-11008
CD66b (3D)	6B,C	1:50, 4 °C for 2 days	Miltenyi Biotec, 130-108-019	Goat anti-human—Alexa Fluor 555	1:100, 6 h at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21433
CD66b (2D)	S2A, Supporting Information	1:200, overnight at 4 °C	Miltenyi Biotec, 130-108-019	Goat anti-human—Alexa Fluor 555	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21433
Cytokeratin-FITC	3C, 4C	1:50, 2 h at 37 °C	Miltenyi Biotec, 130-118-964			
Fibronectin	2B	1:200, overnight at 4 °C	Agilent, A0245	Donkey anti-rabbit—Alexa Fluor 647	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-31573
H3cit (3D)	6C	1:200, 4 °C for 2 days	Abcam, ab281584	Goat anti-rabbit—Alexa Fluor 488	1:100, 6 h at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-11008
H3cit (2D)	S2A, Supporting Information	1:500, overnight at 4 °C	Abcam, ab281584	Goat anti-rabbit—Alexa Fluor 488	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-11008
Ki67	4C	1:25, 2 h at 37 °C	Abcam, ab16667	Donkey anti-rabbit—Alexa Fluor 647	1:100, 1 h at 37 °C	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-31573
NE (3D)	6B,C	1:50, 4 °C for 2 days	R&D systems, MAB91671	Goat anti-mouse—Alexa Fluor 647	1:100, 6 h at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21235
NE (2D)	S6A Supporting Information	1:100, overnight at 4 °C	R&D systems, MAB91671	Goat anti-mouse—Alexa Fluor 647	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21235
MPO (3D)	6C	1:100, 4 °C for 2 days	Miltenyi Biotec, 130-122-342	Goat anti-human—Alexa Fluor 555	1:100, 6 h at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21433
MPO (2D)	S2A, Supporting Information	1:200, overnight at 4 °C	Miltenyi Biotec, 130-122-342	Goat anti-human—Alexa Fluor 555	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A-21433
Vimentin-Alexa Fluor 405	3C, 4C	1:25, 2 h at 37 °C	R&D systems, IC2105V			
Vimentin	2B	1:200, 4 °C overnight	R&D systems, MAB2105	Goat anti-rat—Alexa Fluor 555	1:500, 45 min at RT	Thermo Fisher Scientific, A48263

FTAL5 and luminescence was measured in triplicates in an opaque 384 well plate (lumitrac 781075, Greiner Bio-One) using the Tristar 5 plate reader (Berthold, Germany).

Live Cell Labeling: For tracking experiments cells were stained with a cell tracker at 1:500 in PBS+ according to manufacturer's instructions. SiHa were stained prior to spheroid generation with Cell Tracker Green CMFDA (C7025, Thermo Fisher Scientific), fibroblasts prior to hydrogel embedding with CellTracker Blue CMAC (C2110, Thermo Fisher Scientific), and PMN prior to perfusion with CellTracker Deep Red (C34565, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Immunofluorescent Cell Staining: For antibody staining of PMNs in 2D, glass coverslips were cleaned with absolute ethanol and dried. Thereafter, glass coverslips were placed on the bottom of the wells of a 48-well plate, coated with poly-D-lysine (PDL, 1%, P7280, Sigma Aldrich) in PBS for 5 min, washed with PBS and dried at RT. 200 000 PMNs per cm² were seeded in RPMI (21875, Gibco) with FCS (5%). PMA (100 nM) was added, well plate with cells was centrifuged for 5 min at 200 × g and incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ in a humidified atmosphere. After 5 h, wells were carefully washed three times with PBS at 200 × g for 5 min, with 300 μL remaining in the wells after each wash to reduce cell loss. Cells were fixed using paraformaldehyde (PFA, 4%, 0335.1, Carl Roth in PBS) for 15 min at RT and washed with PBS as described before. 3D tissues and fibroblast monolayers were washed in PBS+ for 5–10 min and fixed with ROTI-Histofix (P087.4, Carl Roth) for 15–30 min, washed with PBS, and stored until further processing at 4 °C in PBS. For independent analysis, chip samples were retrieved and stained in a 96-well plate. For permeabilization and blocking of unspecific bindings, triton (0.1%, X100, Sigma Aldrich) and BSA (3%, A9647, Sigma Aldrich) in PBS were added for 30 min (monolayers) or 45–60 min (3D tissues) at RT. Primary antibodies (50 μL) were applied as summarized in **Table 2** in background reducing antibody diluent (S302283-2, Agilent) and washed with IHC wash buffer (WL583C0500, DCS Innovative Diagnostik-Systeme) for 30 min on mono-layer samples and 7 h for staining of PMNs in Figure 6B,C at RT, and 1.5 h at 37 °C for staining of Figures 3C and 4C. Secondary antibodies (50 μL) were added if applicable as summarized in Table 2 and samples were washed in IHC wash buffer before storage at 4 °C until microscopic analysis.

Image Acquisition and Analyses: Images were obtained using the inverted fluorescent microscope (Axio Observer 7, Zeiss, Germany) and confocal Laser-Scanning-Microscope (LSM 880, Zeiss, Germany), as indicated. Images were processed by adjusting brightness and contrast using ZEN lite Software (Version 3.4, Zeiss), applying the same settings to all images within an experiment. For quantification of fluorescent intensities, the mean gray values of the entire tissue were determined using ImageJ2, with the detailed macros available in the Supporting Information (S1, Supporting Information).

Statistical Analysis: All data was analyzed using GraphPad Prism 9.3.1, bar graphs depict mean ± standard deviation (SD) with sample sizes as stated for each case individually. For testing statistical significance, one-way ANOVA with Holm-Sidak's multiple comparisons test was performed as stated in each graph. Significance is stated as values for $p > 0.05$, one asterisk for $p \leq 0.05$, two asterisks for $p \leq 0.01$, and three asterisks for $p \leq 0.001$.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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